

RELIABILITY OF STIFFNESS PREDICTIONS FOR FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The influence of micromechanic modelling and constituent material property data accuracy on the reliability of unidirectional ply stiffness predictions is examined. Case studies are presented which demonstrate the dangers inherent in back calculating fibre properties from tests on laminate specimens, particularly if fibre properties are then used as input data for other micromechanics theories. A statistical study is made of the sensitivity of common micromechanics theories to their input parameters. The results demonstrate that the prediction of longitudinal modulus of the composite is the most sensitive to the fibre data, and the prediction of the inplane shear stiffness is the least sensitive.

INTRODUCTION

Judging by the number of so called "theories of failure" for composite materials that are in common use it would seem that little confidence can be placed on our ability to predict the strength properties of components made from such materials. It is often overlooked that the same applies to predictions of deformations. The reliability with which predictions of stiffness properties (and hence deformations) can be made depend on several factors. These include the accuracy of the property data for individual constituents of the composite, the validity of the various assumptions invoked in micromechanic modelling, and the idealisations introduced in orthotropic characterisations. The classical assumption of homogeneous orthotropy which provides the basis of off-axis stiffness predictions is rarely questioned. However, recent studies by Battley [1] have demonstrated that at high strain levels, or with large differences in constituent material stiffnesses, fibre rotations can occur which invalidate the orthotropic assumptions.

In this paper, the influence of micromechanic modelling and constituent material property data accuracy on the reliability of unidirectional ply stiffness predictions is examined. The first part of the paper presents results from a series of case studies which demonstrate the dangers inherent in back calculating fibre properties from tests on laminate specimens. Part two of the paper presents a statistical study in which an attempt is made to characterise the sensitivity of common micromechanics theories to their input parameters. The effect, on the predicted ply properties, of the changes in input parameters is calculated for each of the selected theories and the results are presented as percentage variations in the ply inplane stiffness.

In classical modelling of fibre composites, the term micromechanics is used to describe the process of calculating the effective on-axis properties of a lamina, based on the microstructural geometry and properties of the constituent fibres and matrix. In the case of mechanical stiffness properties, the classical micromechanics problem can be simply stated as: Knowing the stiffnesses of the fibres and the matrix, and some details of the microstructural geometry of the composite, what are the effective on-axis stiffnesses of a unidirectional ply.

A wide range of micromechanical theories has been developed for fibre reinforced composites. The theories range from very simple models through to sophisticated elasticity solutions. Several reviews, such as those by Hashin [2] and Tewary [3], have been published on micromechanical theories. Table 1 lists the theories that are included in this paper. The references listed in the table provide details of the theories.

Table 1. Micromechanics theories used in this paper

Micromechanics Theory	Abbreviation	References
Rule of Mixtures	ROM	[4]
ROM with transverse Poisson's effects	ROMP	[5]
Theoretical stress partitioning	StrPart	[5]
Chamis' simplified equations	Chamis	[6]
Composite Cylinder Assemblage model	CCA	[7]

The chosen theories range from the very simple Voight and Reuss solutions of the ROM through to the moderately sophisticated CCA model. While many more sophisticated theories exist, the theories in Table 1 are examples of the types that are in common use, many of them being incorporated in commercial and company in-house composites analysis software packages.

Due to the infinite number of possible combinations of materials in a fibre reinforced composite, it is not possible to provide examples that are directly relevant to every situation. However the results presented in this paper are based on the relatively generic combination of T300 type carbon fibres combined with an epoxy resin. The ply data used as the basis for the analyses was obtained from mechanical tests of tubular specimens [1] constructed from 6 plies of Graphil 6 mil unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg, with a measured fibre volume fraction of 0.54. The back calculations, forward calculations and sensitivity studies were carried out with a purpose written PASCAL computer programme.

BACK CALCULATION OF FIBRE STIFFNESS PROPERTIES

The material properties of the constituents play a crucial role in the accuracy of any micromechanical prediction. Epoxy resins are basically isotropic and the stiffnesses of various formulations are well documented. Reliable mechanical tests can easily be carried out on resin samples. However, the size and geometry of typical fibres (diameters of the order of 10 μm) render mechanical tests difficult and in some cases virtually impossible to perform. Longitudinal stiffness is the only fibre property which can be readily measured, and even in this case alternative methods give different results [8]. The fibre axial shear modulus can be measured by a torsion pendulum but the results are not considered to be very reliable [7]. The fibre transverse stiffness, Poisson's ratios and transverse shear modulus are all extremely difficult to measure.

Isotropic fibres such as glass can be characterised by measuring the longitudinal stiffness and estimating the Poisson's ratio. However carbon fibres are highly anisotropic, typically being treated as transversely isotropic with five required stiffness coefficients [9]. Due to the difficulty of direct measurement of fibre properties a common approach taken (in the case of isotropic fibres also) is to measure on-axis composite ply properties and then use a micromechanical model to back calculate the fibre properties. Clearly the fibre properties estimated by such a process depend on the micromechanical theory used. Unfortunately many fibre properties quoted in the literature do not define how the values were obtained. If the data was obtained by back calculation by a different theory than is subsequently used for the forward calculation then the predicted ply properties can be significantly in error.

The first case study demonstrates the range of fibre properties predicted by different micromechanics theories. The effect of variations in resin stiffness is calculated, then the errors generated by forward calculating from different fibre data are summarised.

BACK CALCULATION WITH DIFFERENT THEORIES

Depending on the micromechanics theory used for back calculation the predicted fibre properties can vary significantly. Table 2 presents the fibre properties calculated by each theory for the same ply properties. The material property notation is defined in Appendix 1.

Table 2. Back calculated carbon fibre properties

Micromechanics Model	Calculated Fibre Engineering Constant					
	E_L	E_T	ν_{LT}	G_{LT}	ν_{TT}	G_{TT}
	GPa	GPa		GPa		GPa
ROM	203	9.3	0.28	89	n/a	n/a
ROM Poisson	203	8.2	0.28	89	n/a	n/a
Stress Partitioning	203	7.7	0.28	9.2	0.30	2.96
Chamis	203	7.6	0.28	6.6	n/a	2.88
CCA	203	7.6	0.28	9.2	0.30	2.88

For $E_m = 5$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.35$, fibre volume fraction = 0.54,
 $E_{LC} = 112$ GPa, $E_{TC} = 6.67$ GPa, $\nu_{LTC} = 0.31$, $G_{LTC} = 3.93$ GPa
 n/a denotes variable not applicable to particular model

As is well known, the ROM theories agree well with the other models for E_{Lf} and ν_{LTf} , however they do not accurately model E_{Tf} or G_{LTf} . The three more sophisticated models provide similar estimates of E_{Tf} . There are very large differences (over 1000% at worst) between the fibre shear moduli calculated by the ROM theories and those calculated by the other approaches. Chamis' equations give a significantly different value (28% lower) for G_{LTf} than the stress partitioning or CCA models.

The stress partitioning and CCA models use ν_{TTf} and E_{Tf} to predict E_T of the composite, resulting in two variables to be extrapolated from one experimental result. Fortunately E_{TC} is only weakly dependent on ν_{TTf} allowing an estimate of ν_{TTf} to be made and then E_{Tf} to be calculated from this and the experimental value for E_{TC} . A parametric study of the two theories revealed that variations in ν_{TTf} from 0.20 to 0.40 caused percentage differences in predicted E_{TC} of only 0.5% and 1% respectively for each of the theories. As the fibres are widely accepted to be transversely isotropic it is unlikely that ν_{TTf} will be outside of this range. An intermediate value of 0.30 was used for this work.

VARIATIONS IN MATRIX MODULUS

Although material properties for different resin systems are reasonably well documented, and mechanical properties for resin samples can be relatively easily measured, it is not always possible to exactly determine the stiffness of the particular resin used. As Table 3 demonstrates, even relatively small differences in matrix properties can have dramatic effects on the calculated fibre properties. The table presents the effect that a 10% variation in the resin modulus has on the fibre properties back calculated by a simple theory (ROM), and by a more sophisticated approach (CCA).

The results highlight the inadequacy of the ROM (and also the ROMP, which is of identical form for G_{LT}) for prediction of inplane shear stiffness. The 10% variation in E_m results in a 79% change in G_{LTf} . The percentage change in the fibre transverse stiffness is also significant at approximately 12%. The CCA is less sensitive to the changes in matrix stiffness than the ROM, with the 10% change in matrix stiffness resulting in 8.9% and 15% changes in the fibre transverse and shear stiffnesses respectively. The shear stiffness back calculations are clearly the most sensitive to any

changes in material property values. As expected, the fibre longitudinal properties (E_{Lf} and ν_{LTf}) are not affected by the small changes in matrix stiffness.

Table 3. Variations in matrix modulus

Theory	Matrix		Fibre			
	E	ν	E_L	E_T	ν_{LT}	G_{LT}
	GPa		GPa	GPa		GPa
ROM	5.0	0.35	203	9.3	0.28	89
ROM	5.2	0.35	203	8.8	0.28	35
ROM	5.5	0.35	203	8.2	0.28	19
CCA	5.0	0.35	203	7.6	0.28	9.2
CCA	5.2	0.35	203	7.3	0.28	8.6
CCA	5.5	0.35	203	7.0	0.28	7.8

FORWARD CALCULATION

Most of the quoted data in the literature for fibre properties does not define how the properties were obtained. As shown in Table 2, using alternative micromechanical models to back calculate the fibre properties can result in very different nominal properties for the fibres. If the values obtained by one method are used as the input data for a different theory, then the predicted composite properties can be greatly in error. Table 4 summarises the errors in the lamina engineering constants generated by using the data from Table 2 as the input for the ROM and CCA theories.

Table 4: Effect of incorrectly sourced fibre property data

Forward Calculation Method	Source of Fibre Properties	% Error in Lamina Engineering Constants			
		E_{Lc}	E_{Tc}	ν_{LTc}	G_{LTc}
		GPa	GPa		GPa
ROM	ROMP	0.00	-4.95	0.00	0.00
ROM	StrPart	0.00	-7.36	0.00	-17.05
ROM	Chamis	0.00	-7.96	0.00	-22.90
ROM	CCA	0.00	-7.96	0.00	-17.05
CCA	ROM	0.00	9.88	-0.96	47.33
CCA	ROMP	0.00	3.59	-0.32	47.33
CCA	StrPrt	0.00	0.75	0.00	0.00
CCA	Chamis	0.00	0.00	0.00	-11.96

The errors are greatest for G_{LT} , the worst case (over 47%) being when using data from the ROM as input for the CCA model. Using a sophisticated theory is of no value unless the input data is appropriate to it! The maximum error in E_{Tc} for this situation is nearly 10%.

SENSITIVITY OF MICROMECHANICS THEORIES

Part one of this paper has demonstrated that it is necessary to take great care when obtaining constituent material properties for use in micromechanical analyses. However no matter what method is used to obtain the properties, there will always be some uncertainty associated with the data. This section of the paper presents the results of a statistical study which determined the sensitivity of each of the micromechanical theories to errors in the fibre stiffness properties. The same computer programme as in the first part of this paper was used to calculate the lamina properties for a range of fibre properties. The errors in the lamina data relative to the nominally correct values were than calculated and graphed. From the results presented here it is possible to determine which of the fibre properties are required to be known to a high degree of accuracy, and which are not as critical.

The predicted properties in the different directions are independent of each other for most of the theories. Although the CCA theory includes some coupling between material properties such as E_{TL} and ν_{LTc} , the effect of this coupling is only of the order of 1% for the range of properties studied here. It is thus possible to summarise the results in only a few graphs.

LONGITUDINAL STIFFNESS

Fig. 1 shows the effect on the composite longitudinal stiffness and Poisson's ratio of $\pm 20\%$ variations in the corresponding fibre properties. All theories predict equal values for E_{LC} and virtually equal for ν_{LTc} , resulting in only a single line for each parameter. Since the expressions for these properties are very simple linear equations it is not surprising that the errors in both composite properties are linearly related to the errors in the fibre properties. As E_{LC} is dominated by E_{Lf} the error in the composite longitudinal stiffness is virtually equal to that in the fibre data. The Poisson's ratios of fibre and matrix are similar, and hence the error in the composite Poisson's ratio is much less than for E_{LC} .

Figure 1. Sensitivity of composite longitudinal stiffness and Poisson's ratio to errors in the corresponding fibre property

Although the prediction of the laminate longitudinal stiffness is very sensitive to the fibre stiffness data, the fibre longitudinal stiffness is the easiest fibre property to measure, and can also be more reliably back calculated than the other fibre properties. Furthermore, in the case of a multidirectional laminate the lamina longitudinal stiffness is often the dominant parameter affecting the accuracy of the overall stiffness predictions for the laminate.

TRANSVERSE STIFFNESS

The results for the transverse case (Fig. 2) and shear stiffness case (Fig. 3) are plotted over a wider range ($\pm 50\%$) than in Fig. 1, as the possible errors in the fibre transverse and shear properties are greater. The errors for the transverse case are different for each of the theories, and are less than for the longitudinal case. Chamis' model is the most sensitive to variations in E_{Tf} , while the other theories are similar. The errors are greater for fibre values that are lower than the actual value than they are for higher values.

Figure 2. Sensitivity of composite transverse stiffness to errors in fibre transverse stiffness

SHEAR STIFFNESS

The results for the shear stiffness case (Fig. 3) are less linear than the other cases. The errors are also smaller than for the other properties. Interestingly, the more "advanced" theories such as Stress Partitioning and CCA are significantly more sensitive than the simple ROM and ROMP models. As in the transverse case, the errors are greater for low fibre values than for high.

Figure 3. Sensitivity of composite shear stiffness to errors in fibre shear stiffness

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained when back calculating fibre properties from lamina data depend greatly on the micromechanics theory used. The theories studied in this paper predict virtually identical values for the fibre longitudinal stiffness and Poisson's ratio, but differ by up to 22% in their predicted transverse stiffness for the fibre. The predicted shear modulus of the fibre can vary by more than 1000% depending on the theory used. The properties of the resin material affect the predicted fibre properties, particularly when used in simple theories such as the ROM. Forward calculating from fibre data sourced from different theories can generate errors in the predicted ply properties of more than 47%.

The lamina property that is the most sensitive to errors in the fibre data is the prediction of longitudinal stiffness. Prediction of the lamina shear stiffness is less sensitive to the fibre properties, but is more sensitive to low fibre properties than to high values. For the prediction of transverse and shear stiffnesses the more sophisticated theories are more sensitive to errors in fibre properties than the simple models.

The overall conclusion of this work is that it is very important to be sure of the origin of any material property data used in a micromechanics calculation. Data obtained from any source should be interpreted with extreme care unless the exact methods used to obtain it are known.

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APPENDIX 1. NOTATION

Figure 5: Axis system

Directions:

- L longitudinal
- T transverse

Material Properties:

- E Young's modulus
- ν major Poisson's ratio
- G inplane shear stiffness

Subscripts f and c designate fibre and composite respectively.

